

Update from Institut Pasteur

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1. Analysis of the P15 light chain with the omnitrap
2. First data with the booster
3. Analysis of the NIST mAb
4. Conclusions/Future direction

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P15: Light chain from urine of patients (multiple myeloma)

De Novo Sequencing of Antibody Light Chain Proteoforms from Patients with Multiple Myeloma

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 Metrics & More

 Article Recommendations

 Supporting Information

Data acquisition status on the HF-Omnitrap-Booster platform

1. Top-down LC-MSn analysis of Light Chains (**HF-Omnitrap**)
Data acquired from April to July 2022, processed with PeakFinder
2. Top-down LC-MSn analysis of Light Chains (**HF-Omnitrap**)
After filament replacement, data acquired from Sept to Oct 2022, to be processed with Cronus
3. Top-down LC-MSn analysis of Light Chains (**Lumos**)
Data acquired in August 2022, to be processed with Cronus
4. HF-Omnitrap-Booster Characterization (**HF-Omnitrap-Booster**)
5. Top-down LC-MSn analysis of NISTmAb (**HF-Omnitrap**)

Reduced, alkylated and intact Light chain: MS1

Reduced, alkylated

Intact

Data acquired from April to July 2022 (nLC + PeakFinder)

Reduced, alkylated LC (m/z 1034, 23+)

Exp.		Seq. coverage	Parameters
	HCD NCE20	36% (deconv.)	AGC5E5,10 μ scan, 240k
MS2	ET10HCD10 (Lumos)	77.9%	AGC1E6,20 μ scan, 120k
	ECD 70ms	78.9%	AGC5E5,10 μ scan, 120k
	EID 50ms	85.0%	AGC5E5,10 μ scan, 120k
	ECD 50ms	83.1%	AGC5E5,10 μ scan, 120k
	ECD 50ms+suppl. CID activation	91.5%	AGC5E5,10 μ scan, 120k 2 datasets combined

Intact LC (m/z 1388, 17+)

Exp.		Seq. coverage	Parameters
MS2	HCD NCE20	20% (deconv.)	AGC5E5,10 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 70ms	37%	AGC5E5,10 μ scan, 120k
	ECD 70ms+suppl. CID activation	44% (deconv.)	AGC5E5,10 μ scan, 120k 2 datasets combined
	EID 50ms		AGC5E5,10 μ scan, 120k
	EID 150ms	39%	AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 250ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 500ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 750ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
MS3	ECD 250ms+MS3CID of 16+•	39.0%	AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 250ms+MS3CID of 15+••	25.4%	AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 500ms+MS3CID of 16+•	41.3%	AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 750ms+MS3CID of 16+•	29.6%	AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	EID 150ms+MS3CID of 18+•	28.2%	AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	EID 150ms+MS3CID of 19+••	23.0%	AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
MS4 y96	HCD20-ECD50ms-MS4CID	33.7% (y96)	AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	HCD20-ECD500ms-MS4CID	26.3% (y96)	AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k

Reduced, alkylated Light chain: ECD (m/z 1034, 23+)

ECD 50 ms

a : 10% x : 14%

b : 9% y : 31%

c : 50% z : 60%

Sequence coverage : 83.1%

Reduced, alkylated Light chain: ECD (m/z 1034, 23+) + CID

ECD 50 ms + CID supp activation

a : 15% x : 15%
 b : 28% y : 51%
 c : 53% z : 62%

2 datasets combined

Sequence coverage : 91.5%

Reduced, alkylated Light chain: EID (m/z 1034, 23+)

EID 50 ms

a : 20% x : 42%

b : 20% y : 31%

c : 21% z : 52%

Sequence coverage : 85%

Reduced, alkylated Light chain: EThCD Lumos

ET10 HCD10 on Lumos

a : 6% x : 1%
 b : 17% y : 31%
 c : 38% z : 53%

Sequence coverage : 77.9%

Intact Light chain: ECD (m/z 1388, 17+)

ECD 70 ms

a : 18% x : 15%
 b : 7% y : 16%
 c : 23% z : 24%

Sequence coverage : 37.1%

DLQMTQSPSTLSASVGDVTLTCRASQSLNVWLAWYQQKPKPKLLLYE
 ASNLESGVPSRFSGSGSGTEFTLTLSSLQPDDFATYYCQQYNSYPYTFGQ
 GAKLELKRVAAPS VFLFPPSDEQLKSGTASVVCLLNNFYPREAKVQWKV
 DNALQSGNSQESVTEQDSKDYSLSSSTLTLISKADYEKHKLYACEVTHQG
 LSSPVTKSFRGEC

a
x
b
y
c
z

Intact Light chain: ECD (m/z 1388, 17+) + CID

HF-Omnitrap

ECD 70 ms + suppl. CID activation

2 datasets combined

Sequence coverage : 44%

N D[L]Q[M]T]Q[S]P]S[T]L]S]A]S]V]G]D]A]V]T]L T C]R A 25
 26 S Q S L N V W L A W Y Q Q K]P G K]P]P K L L L Y E 50
 51 A S N L E S G V]P S R F S G S G S G T E F T]L T L 75
 76]S]S]L]Q]P D]D]F A]T Y]Y C]Q]Q]Y]N]S]Y]P]Y]T]F]G]Q 100
 101]G]A]K]L]E]L]K]R]T V]A]A]P]S]V]F]L]F]P]P]S]D]E]Q L 125
 126]K]S]G]T]A]S]V]V C] L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V 150
 151 D N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S K D S T Y S L 175
 176 S S T L T L S K A D Y E K H K L Y A C]E]V]T]H]Q]G 200
 201]L]S]S]P V]T]K]S]F N R G]E]C C

Intact Light chain: EID (m/z 1388, 17+)

EID 150 ms

a : 15% x : 25%

b : 12% y : 17%

c : 13% z : 19%

Sequence coverage : 39%

DLQMTQSPSTLSASVGDVTLTCRASQSLNVWLAWYQQKPK
 GKPKLLLYEASNLESGVPSRFSGSGSGTEFTLTLSSLQP
 DDFATYYCQQYNSYPYTFGQGAKLELKRITVAAPSVFLFPP
 SDEQLKSGTASVVCLLNNFYPREAKVQWKVDNALQSGNSQ
 ESVTEQDSKDSSTYSLSSTLTLTKADYEKHKLYACEVTHQG
 LSSPVTKSFNRGEC

Intact Light chain: MS3

ECD 250 ms, MS3 CID of m/z 1475 (16+•)

a : 10% x : 7%

b : 22% y : 19%

c : 14% z : 14%

Sequence coverage : 39%

DLQMTQSPSTLSASVGDVTLT**C**RASQSLNVWLAWYQQKPKPKLLLYE
 ASNLESGVPSRFSGSGSGTEFTLTLSSLQPDDFATYY**C**QQYNSYPYTFGQ
 GAKLELKRTVAAPS^aVFLFPPSDEQLKSGTASVV**C**LLN^xNFYPREAKVQWKV
 DNALQSGNSQESVTEQDSKDYSLSSSTLTL**C**SKADYEKHKLYA**C**EVTHQG
 LSSPVT**K**SFNRG**E****C**

Legend:
 a: green
 x: red
 b: blue
 y: cyan
 c: magenta
 z: black

Intact Light chain: MS3

ECD 500 ms, MS3 CID of m/z 1475 (16+•)

a : 11% x : 9%

b : 28% y : 21%

c : 15% z : 17%

Sequence coverage : 41.3%

Intact Light chain: MS3

ECD 750 ms, MS3 CID of m/z 1475 (16+•)

a : 9% x : 6%
 b : 15% y : 16%
 c : 13% z : 11%

Sequence coverage : 29.6%

Intact Light chain: MS3

EID 150 ms, MS3 CID of m/z 1311 (18+•)

a : 8% x : 8%
 b : 19% y : 13%
 c : 8% z : 9%

Sequence coverage : 28.2%

DLQMTQSPSTLSASVGDVTLT **C**RASQSLNVWLAWYQQKPGKPPKLLLYE
 ASNLESGVPSRFSGSGSGTEFTLTLSLQPDDFATYY **C**QQYNSYPYTFGQ
 GAKLELKRTVAAPS **V**FLFPSSDEQLKSGTASVV **C**LLNMFYPREAKVQWKV
 DNALQSGNSQESVTEQDSKDYSLSSSTLTLSKADYEKHKLYA **C**EVTHQG
 LSSPVTKSFRGEC

Legend: a (green), x (red), b (blue), y (cyan), c (orange), z (purple)

Intact Light chain: MS3

EID 150 ms, MS3 CID of m/z 1242 (19+••)

a : 6% x : 7%

b : 13% y : 13%

c : 6% z : 10%

Sequence coverage : 23%

DLQMTQSPSTLSASVGDVTLT**C**RASQSLNVWLAWYQQKPKPKLLLYE
 ASNLESGVPSRFSGSGSGTEFTLTLSSLQPDDFATYY**C**QQYNSYPYTFGQ
 GAKLELKRTVAAPS**V**FLFPSSDEQLKSGTASVV**C**LLNMFYPREAKVQWKV
 DNALQSGNSQESVTEQDSKDYSLSSSTLTL**S**KADYEKHKLYA**C**EVTHQG
 LSSPVTK**S**FN**R**GE**C**

┌ a
└ x
┌ b
└ y
┌ c
└ z

Intact Light chain: MS4

HCD NCE20

HF-Omnitrap

```
N D L Q M T Q S P S T L S A S V G D A V T L T C R A 25
26 S Q S L N V W L A W Y Q Q K P G K P P K L L L Y E 50
51 A S N L E S G V P S R F S G S G S G T E F T L T L 75
76 S S L Q P D D F A T Y Y C Q Q Y N S Y P Y T F G Q 100
101 G A K L E L K R T V A A P S V F L L F P P S D E Q L 125
126 K S G T A S V V C L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V 150
151 D N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S K D S T Y S L 175
176 S S T L T L S K A D Y E K H K L Y A C E V T H Q L G 200
201 L L S S P V T K S F N R G E C C
```

y96

Intact Light chain: MS4

MS2 **HCD** NCE 20

Res DC isolation

MS3 **ECD** 50 ms

Res DC isolation

MS4 **CID**

NL: 2.2E6

HF-Omnitrap

NL: ~ 4.6E5

NL: 4.0E5

NL: 5.6E4

NL: 5.0E3

Intact Light chain: MS4

MS2 HCD20-MS3 ECD 50ms-MS4 CID

HF-Omnitrap

P P S D E Q L K S G T A S V V C L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V D N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S
K D S T Y S L S S T L T L S K A D Y E K H K L Y A C E V T H Q G L S S P V T K S F N R G E C

a
x
b
y
c
z

a : 1% x : 5%
b : 11% y : 24%
c : 15% z : 13%

Sequence coverage : 33.7%

Intact Light chain: MS4 (extending MS3 ECD activation time)

Sequence coverage : 33.7%

Sequence coverage : 26.3%

Data acquired in Sept./Oct. 2022, to be processed w. Cronus

Reduced, alkylated LC (*m/z* 1034, 23+)

Exp.		Seq. coverage	Parameters
MS2	ECD 25ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 50ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 100ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 50ms ^a		AGC5E5,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 50ms+suppl. CID activation (<i>m/z</i> 1081) ^a		AGC5E5,3 μ scan, 240k
	EID 25 ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	EID 50ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k

^a AGC target was lowered to 1E6 to obtain charge reduced species

Intact LC (*m/z* 1388, 17+)

Exp.		Seq. coverage	Parameters
MS2	ECD 50 ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 100ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 100ms+suppl. CID activation		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 200ms		AGC5E5,3 μ scan, 240k
	ECD 250ms		AGC5E5,3 μ scan, 240k
	EID 50ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	EID 100ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	MS3	ECD 100ms+MS3CID of 16+•	
ECD 200ms+MS3CID of 16+•			AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
EID 50ms+MS3CID of 18+•			AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
MS3 (y96)	HCD20-EID 50ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	HCD20-EID 200ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	HCD20-ECD 50ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	HCD20-ECD 500ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
MS4 (y96)	HCD20-ECD50ms-MS4CID		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	HCD20-ECD500ms-MS4CID		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	In source CID- <i>m/z</i> 1339-ECD50ms-MS4CID		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	In source CID- <i>m/z</i> 1339-ECD500ms-MS4CID		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
MS3 (b118)	In source CID- <i>m/z</i> 1432-ECD50ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
MS4 (b118)	In source CID- <i>m/z</i> 1432-ECD500ms		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	In source CID- <i>m/z</i> 1432-ECD50ms-MS4CID		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k

Intact Light chain: MS4 (m/z 1388, 17+)

Targeting C terminal fragment *y96 ion* HCD NCE20

```
N D L Q M T Q S P S T L S A S V G D A V T L T C R A 25
26 S Q S L N V W L A W Y Q Q K P G K P P K L L Y E 50
51 A S N L E S G V P S R F S G S G S G T E F T L T L 75
76 S S L Q P D D F A T Y Y C Q Q Y N S Y P Y T F G Q 100
101 G A K L E L K R T V A A P S V F L F P P S D E Q L 125
126 K S G T A S V V C L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V 150
151 D N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S K D S T Y S L 175
176 S S T L T L S K A D Y E K H K L Y A C E V T H Q G 200
201 L S S P V T K S F N R G E C C
```

y96

Intact Light chain: MS4 (m/z 1388, 17+)

Targeting N terminal fragment *b118 ion*

HCD NCE20

```
N D L Q M T Q S P S T L S A S V G D A V T L T C R A 25
26 S Q S L N V W L A W Y Q Q K P G K P P K L L L Y E 50
51 A S N L E S G V P S R F S G S G S G T E F T L T L 75
76 S S L Q P D D F A T Y Y C Q Q Y N S Y P Y T F G Q 100
101 G A K L E L K R T V A A P S V F L F P P S D E Q L 125
126 K S G T A S V V C L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V 150
151 D N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S K D S T Y S L 175
176 S S T L T L S K A D Y E K H K L Y A C E V T H Q G 200
201 L L S S P V T K S F N R G E C C
```

b118

y96

Data acquired on Lumos (Aug. 2022) to be processed with Cronus

Lumos

Reduced, alkylated LC (m/z 1034, 23+)

Intact LC (m/z 1388, 17+)

	Exp.	Seq. coverage	Parameters
MS2 ^d	ETD10		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ET5HCD5		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ET10HCD10		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ET15HCD15		AGC5E5,3 μ scan, 240k

^d Low AGC target data (1E6, 3 and 10 μ scan) were also acquired

	Exp.	Seq. coverage	Parameters
MS2 ^a	ETD15		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ETD20		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ETD25		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ET10HCD10		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ET15HCD15		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ET10HCD10		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	ET25HCD25		AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
	MS3 ^b (m/z 1475, 16+)	ETD-MS3HCD15	
ETD-MS3HCD20			AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
ETD-MS3HCD25			AGC5E6,3 μ scan, 240k
MS3 ^c (m/z 1339, 8+, y96)	HCD-MS3ETD15		AGC1E6,10 μ scan, 240k
	HCD-MS3ETD20		AGC1E6,10 μ scan, 240k
	HCD-MS3ET15HCD15		AGC1E6,10 μ scan, 240k
	HCD-MS3ET20HCD20		AGC1E6,10 μ scan, 240k

^a Low AGC target data (1E6, 3 and 10 μ scan) were also acquired

^b Low AGC target data (1E6, 10 μ scan) were also acquired

^c High AGC target data (5E6, 3 μ scan) were not usable

Cronus analysis

The screenshot displays the Cronus software interface, which is a workflow editor for mass spectrometry data analysis. The interface is organized into several sections:

- Menu Bar:** File, Edit, Libraries, UI Settings.
- Workflow Editor:** Spectrum Plot, Fitting Graphs.
- Primitive Nodes:** Spectrum, Amino Acid Sequence, RNA Sequence.
- Processing Nodes:** Peak Picker, Spectrum Resampler, Spectrum Calibration, Fragment Generator.
- Algorithm Nodes:** mMass Isotope Clustering, Spectrum Fitter, De Novo Sequencing.
- Utility Nodes:** Fragment Combiner, Mod Cross Product.

The main workspace shows a workflow with the following nodes and connections:

- Spectrum Node:** Spectrum Information: Spectrum File: C:\Users\vcgarci\Desktop\20220919_QHF_TF_P15. The spectrum has 1350292 m/z - intensity pairs. (Remove Spectrum button)
- Peak Picker Node:** Connected Spectrum Info: # Points: 1350292, # Peaks: 14972.
- Fragment Generator Node:** Input Sequence Information: Name: New Unnamed Sequence, Length: 214 Amino Acids, Extension: (Select Fragments, Select Charge States, Run Fragment Generator, View Fragment List buttons). Charge states are set from 1 to 25.
- Spectrum Fitter Node:** Input Spectrum Name: 20220919_QHF_TF_P15_LC_intactL_ECD50_mz. Spectrum Connected, Input Fragments: # Loaded: 52198, # Filtered: 670. Filtering Parameters: ei Score Threshold: 0.850, Normalized XCorr Threshold: 0.200, Alignment Score Threshold: 0.700. (Calculate Isotopic Distributions button).

Connections: The Spectrum node connects to the Peak Picker node. The Peak Picker node connects to the Spectrum Fitter node. The Fragment Generator node connects to the Spectrum Fitter node.

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HF-Omnitrap-Booster Characterization

LC-MSn analysis of red/alkyl Light chain

ECD 50 ms, 15k resolution, 5 replicates

QExHF, TF_P15_LCs_red_alkyl_ECD50, R = 15 K , AGC = 5e5, ITmax = 200 ms

20220712_QHF_TF_P15_LCs_red_alkyl_ECD50_15k_R1

HF-Omnitrap-Booster

QExHF, TF_P15_LCs_red_alkyl_ECD50, R1

HF-Omnitrap-Booster

dataset key: "253391" (scan number in RAW file: #3724)

- RAW, eFT, Tacq = 32 ms
- H5, aFT (half), Tacq = 45 ms

- RAW, eFT, Tacq = 32 ms
- H5, aFT (full), Tacq = 150 ms

QExHF, TF_P15_LCs_red_alkyl_ECD50, R = 120 K

AGC = 5e5, ITmax = 200 ms

ECD 50 ms, 120k resolution, 5 replicates

QExHF, TF_P15_LCs_red_alkyl_ECD50, R = 120 K AGC = 5e5, ITmax = 200 ms

20220712_QHF_TF_P15_LCs_red_alkyl_ECD50_120k_R1

HF-Omnitrap-Booster

QExHF, TF_P15_LCs_red_alkyl_ECD50, R = 120 K

AGC = 5e5, ITmax = 200 ms

QExHF, TF_P15_LCs_red_alkyl_ECD50, R = 120 K, AGC = 5e5, ITmax = 200 ms

HF-Omnitrap-Booster

Single scan

dataset key: "4149" (scan number in RAW file: #3319)

- RAW, eFT, Tacq = 256 ms
- H5, aFT (half), Tacq = 256 ms

QExHF, TF_P15_LCs_red_alkyl_ECD50, R = 120 K

AGC = 5e5, ITmax = 200 ms

QExHF, TF_P15_LCs_red_alkyl_ECD50, R = 120 K , **AGC = fixed**, ITmax = 50 ms, **10 us**

20220712_QHF_TF_P15_LCs_red_alkyl_ECD50_120k_10μscan_AGC_fixed_1

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HF-Omnitrap: TDMS analysis of Intact antibody

HF-Omnitrap

Intact NISTmAb, m/z 2797, 53+

Isolation window: 30 m/z

MS2 ECD 90 ms

MS2 ECD 90 ms +
Broadband excitation

Sequence coverage obtained from MS2 ECD

+BB excitation

ECD 90 ms +
Broadband excitation

Residue cleavage: 16%

N D I Q M T Q S P S T L S A S V G D R V T I T C S A 25
 26 S S R V G Y M H W Y Q Q K P G K A P K L L I Y D T 50
 51 S K L A S G V P S R F S G S G S G T E F T L T I S 75
 76 S L Q P D D F A T Y Y C F Q G S G Y P F T F G G G 100
 101 T K V E I K R T V A A P S V F I F P S D E Q L K 125
 126 S G T A S V V C L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V D 150
 151 N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S K D S T Y S L S 175
 176 S T L T L S K A D Y E K H K V Y A C E V T H Q G L 200
 201 S S P V T K S F N R G E C C

Residue cleavage: 21%

N Q V T L R E S G P A L V K P T Q T L T L T C T F S 25
 26 G F S L S T A G M S V G W I R Q P P G K A L E W L 50
 51 A D I W W D D K K H Y N P S L K D R L T I S K D T 75
 76 S K N Q V V L K V T N M D P A D T A T Y Y C A R D 100
 101 M I F N F Y F D V W G Q G T T V T V S S A S T K G 125
 126 P S V F P L A P S S K S T S G G T A A L G C L V K 150
 151 D Y F P E P V T V S W N S G A L T S G V H T F P A 175
 176 V L Q S S G L Y S L S S V V T V P S S S L G T Q T 200
 201 Y I C N V N H K P S N T K V D K R V E P K S C D K 225
 226 T H T C P P C P A P E L L G G P S V F L F P P K P 250
 251 K D T L M I S R T P E V T C V V V D V S H E D P E 275
 276 V K F N W Y V D G V E V H N A K T K P R E E Q Y N 300
 301 S T Y R V V S V L T V L H Q D W L N G K E Y K C K 325
 326 V S N K A L L P A P I E K T I L S K A K G Q P R E L P Q 350
 351 V Y T L L P P S R E E M T K N Q V L S L T C L V K G F 375
 376 Y P S D I A V E W E S N G Q P E N N Y K T T P P V 400
 401 L D S D G S F F L Y S K L T V D K S R W Q Q G N V 425
 426 F S C S V M H E A L H N H Y T Q K S L S L S P G C

MSn experiments

MS2: CID of m/z 2797 (53+)

MS2: CID + broadband excitation

MS3: ECD of light chain 10+

MS4: ...

Lumos ETD 15 ms

m/z 2797, 53+, isolation window: 2 m/z

Residue cleavage: 10%

N Q V T L R E **S** G P **A** L **V** K P **T** Q **T** L **T** L **T** **C** T F S 25
 26 G F S L S T A G M S V G W I R Q P P G K A L E W L 50
 51 A D I W W D D K K H Y N P S L K D R L T I S K D T 75
 76 S K N Q V V L K V T N M D P A D T A T Y Y **C** A **R** D 100
 101 **M** I **F** **N** **F** **Y** **F** **D** V W G **Q** G T T V T V S S A S **T** **K** **G** 125
 126 P S V **F** F P L A P S S K S T S G **G** T A A L G **C** L V K 150
 151 D Y F P E P V T V S W N S G A L T S G V H T F P A 175
 176 V L Q S S G L Y S L S S V V T V P S S S L G T Q T 200
 201 Y I **C** N V N H K P S N T K V D K R V E P K S **C** D K 225
 226 T H T **C** P P **C** P A P E L L G G P S V F L F P P K P 250
 251 K D T L M I S R T P E V T **C** V V V D V S H E D P E 275
 276 V K F N W Y V D G V E V H N A K T K P R E E Q Y **N** 300
 301 S T Y R V V S V L T V L H Q D W L N G K E Y K **C** **L** **K** 325
 326 V S **N** **K** **A** **L** **L** P A P **I** **E** **K** **T** **I** **L** **S** **K** **A** **K** **G** **Q** **P** **R** **E** **P** **L** **Q** 350
 351 V Y T **L** P P S R E **E** **M** **T** **K** **N** **Q** **V** **S** L T **C** L V K G F 375
 376 Y P S D I A V E W E S N G Q P E N N Y K T T P P V 400
 401 L D S D G S F F L Y S K L T V D K S R W Q Q G N V 425
 426 F S **C** S V M H E A L H **N** H Y T **Q** **K** S L S L S P G **C**

Residue cleavage: 9%

N D I Q M T Q S P S T L S A S V G D R V T I T **C** S A 25
 26 S S R V G Y M H W **Y** **Y** Q Q K P G K A P K L L I Y D T 50
 51 S K L A S G V P S R F S G S G S G T E F T L T I S 75
 76 S L Q P D D F A T Y Y **C** F Q G **S** G **Y** **P** **F** **T** **F** G G G 100
 101 **T** **K** V E **I** **K** R T V A **A** **P** S V **F** **I** **F** P P S D E **Q** **L** **K** 125
 126 S G T A S V V **C** L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V D 150
 151 N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S K D S T Y S L S 175
 176 S T L T L S K A D Y E K H K V Y A **C** E V T H Q G L 200
 201 S S P V T K S F N R G E **C** **C**

Contents

1. Analysis of the P15 light chain with the omnitrap
2. First data with the booster
3. Analysis of the NIST mAb
4. Conclusions/Future direction

Conclusions/future directions

- Easy and smooth installation (3 days), very stable system (filament changed only once, no other major cleaning), but manual operation (4-5 LC-MS/MS experiments /day)
- Very promising data both on light chain (LC time scale) and mAb analysis
- Added value of booster for data acquisition
- Data analysis very long and difficult (improved with Cronus but still requires more automation)

- **To be done (by Dec 2022?)**
 - Analyse all acquired data and **acquire new ones on intact mAbs (infusion) with the booster (C. Garcia)**
 - Install and test the PI trap
 - Install VUV on the omnitrap
 - Write the paper on the P15 light chain (> ASMS abstracts)

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